

Management of Lifestyle Disorders Through Ahar

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Introduction:

Life is a part of nature. Nature is a part of life. So, life and nature influence each other. Life runs in a disciplined way. Nature governs life on the basis of different principles of governance. So, nature administers over the world through these universal principles of governance. Life is bound to obey all those principles set by nature. But when life doesn't obey the disciplines or orders of nature it invites so many disorders in the form of death, disease, destruction, natural calamities, and so on. Yoga is a powerful key to establishing a healthy relationship between life and nature. So, each of us should understand the positive effects of yoga on human life not only to establish social wellbeing rather to save the generations from the ultimate destruction. In one sentence the practice and practicality of yoga supersedes its theory in the past, present, and future.

Keywords: Ahara, Satwik, Rajasik, Tamasik, charbya, chosya, lehya

Objectives:

- To understand lifestyle disorders.
- To know the mechanism of controlling lifestyle disorders.
- To implicate yogic principles in day-to-day life.

- To discuss different types of foods and their effect on the mind.
- To bring positive changes in the food habits of the youngsters.
- To address the problems relating to modern food habits.

Relevance of the study:

It is a strong belief in the spiritual world that people in Satya yuga could exist till the existence of their bones. People in Treta yuga could survive till the existence of skin. People in Dwapar yuga could live till the existence of their flesh and blood. But in this kali yuga, we possess an annagata prana or the life of anna brahma. Anna or rice has its unique significance in comparison to other food components that we take in our day-to-day life. It's noteworthy that rice is replaced by many other foods such as roti, paratha, nan, and kulcha. These foods are made out of millet, bajra, barley, jawar, wheat, etc. but no corn other than rice is taken as Brahma so we should try to understand the value of annabrahma in this article.

There is a discrepancy between modern and traditional food habits. These changes in food habits have changed the natural balance of body and mind which causes both physical and mental disorders creating multiple health complications. Our changing food habits have changed our attitude and mindset towards life. It has also affected our food culture and invited diseased and crippled conditions and young ages before approaching old age, which naturally comes in the fourth stage of life. So, understanding all the evil effects of modern food patterns and western food culture we need to go back to our Indian food habits to control all those on timely face unwanted diseases like high blood pressure, hypertension, mental illness, obesity, diabetes, and other health complications which are going day by day threatening India to be the capital of all those diseases. So, this article tries to highlight all those evil effects of modern food habits and tries to address all those problems by creating awareness regarding the cultural and scientific food habits inspired by our Indigenous health knowledge covered under the Indian Knowledge System.

Lifestyle disorders cause and consequences:

From the astrological point of view, man should live a life of 120 years, if not 100 years under four stages i.e. Brahmacharya, Grahastya, Banabrahtha, and Sanyasa each of 25 years. But unfortunately living a life of 60 years in good condition has become a challenge for so many people in the country. Hence complications like diabetes and high blood pressure occur during young adulthood. The occurrence of menarche becomes earlier than before even within 10 years of age in some cases like this different health complications relating to women's health are increasing day by day. The rates of breast cancer, cervical cancer, and liver cirrhosis are seen at a large scale in society. The sexual ability of males is being reduced due to these food effects. The increasing rate of sexual attitudes at early ages develops criminal attitudes and threatens women's security and social discipline at this age. Due to the hormonal effect and chemical effects, it needs to put on thick glasses at an early age to protect the eyes from refractive errors. Formalin used in fish causes abdominal discomfort, vomiting, and renal injury, those who cannot avoid non-vegetarian food at least take precautionary measures to save their body from the destructive effect of formalin- thorough washing remove formalin up to some extent, cooking at 75 degrees or above removes the same, the consumers can adulteration test by using CIF kit developed by ICAR-CIFT to know the amount of formalin in fish. The rate of suicide is increasing in spite of the rapid growth of education as modern food habits cause serious damage to the peace of mind and balance of the brain for which people lose their temper and feel the problems caused by the laxity of self-governance and social tolerance in their sophisticated life. The increasing rate of heart attacks not only causes the untimely death of people rather it increases the treatment expenses which usually breaks the backbone of the family, our instant pleasure in enjoying food invites diabetes which imposes unnecessary food restrictions throughout life so these are the common disorders and bad consequences of our ill food habits which need to be addressed through the educational campaign by incorporating those issues in our school and college curriculum.

Mechanism of controlling lifestyle disorders:

You can control all these lifestyle disorders by taking suitable precautions as soon as possible. We can adopt a simple scientific and healthy life to avoid all those health complications occurring untimely in our lives. We should try to adopt an ideal traditional Indian lifestyle to avoid all those unwanted diseases from our lives. We should make different health issues-related orientation programmes and awareness campaigns in our school and college curricula in an age-appropriate manner. We should try to give off or minimise our temptation for fast food to make us fit and healthy. We should prefer chemical-free natural food preferably vegetarian food items to strengthen our digestive system. We should adopt regional food and seasonal foods understanding the relation of the food with nature. We should make fruits and vegetables and other fireless cooked food included in our lunch and dinner.

Different types of food and their effect on the mind:

We can take three examples from our Indian scriptures to understand the effect of food and mind and life as well. As per the description in the Mahabharat pita maha Bhisma on his sarasarjya (arrow bed) was asked about the cause of his silence during the Draupadi's atrocity in the Kuru sabha. Pita maha gave a significant reply to the Pandavas that the only cause of supporting such an injustice against sati Draupadi was nothing but the effect of food offered by Duryodhan the supporter and consumer of injustice. The second example can be taken from Ramayana. It was that time when Bharat, Shatrughna, along with his courtiers were moving towards Chitrakut to bring lord Sri Ram back to Ayodhya. While younger Laxman watched them coming towards Chitrakut, asked the tribal king Guhak regarding their further course of action. King Guhak asked his minister to make a plan to understand the mindset of Bharat and his companions well in advance so that they could do something in favour of lord Sri Ram, Devi Sita, and Anuja Laxman. Now, the old minister adopted a technique of studying the minds through food. They arranged three types of food together to study the psychology of young Prince Bharat. In the first part, they put wine and meat, if Bharat would take them, they would understand that he was coming for war. In the second part,

they offered rice, dal, and curry so that if Bharat would take them, they would consider that they were coming for any kind of treaty or agreement. In the third part, they offered milk and fruits so that if Bharat would accept them, he should be predicted to have come with a positive intention and welcome them accordingly. The science behind this simple testing mechanism through food is that satwik aharas restore peace everywhere in the mind, families, and in society. Rajasik ahar calculates the worldly relations within an exchange of offerings in the form of work, words, love or anything else. The tamasic ahara usually generates violence and evil attitudes to protect one's own interest at the cost of anything and everything.

The third example explains that King Bhanupratap a character of Ramayana offered meat to some Brahmins. Though he did so unknowingly still he was cursed by the Brahmins and became Ravana in his following life. It means killing and offering animals for food is taken as a sin in the Hindu Vaishnav culture. Sin or not, non-vegetarian food makes our digestive system ineffective in due course of time. The effect of formalin used for the preservation of fish and hormonal injections used for the growth of the roasters have micro effects upon the human nervous system for example those children who take eggs frequently are exposed to refractive errors followed by compulsory use of lenses. We can take chapter 17, verse 8 of Shrimad Bhagavat Gita to understand the science of food and their tremendous effect on human life which are as follows:

आयुःसत्त्वबलारोग्यसुखप्रीतिविवर्धनाः ।

रस्याः स्निग्धाः स्थिरा हृद्या आहाराः सात्त्विकप्रियाः ॥ ८ ॥

Aayuh sattwabalaarogya sukha preetivi vardhanaah;

Rasyaah snigdhaah sthiraah hridayaa aahaaraah saattwikapriyaah

Satwik aharas brings us purity in thought, health, joy in mind, strength of the body, longevity of life, and other positive health perspectives. Milk and foods, greens and vegetables and sprouts, fruit juice, leaf extracts, and honey of different seeds are such

kinds of foods. The more satwik ahara we take the better immunity we possess to fight against diseases and environmental pollution.

कट्वम्ललवणात्युष्णतीक्ष्णरूक्षविदाहिनः ।

आहारा राजसस्येष्टा दुःखशोकामयप्रदाः ॥ ९ ॥

Katvamlalavanaatyushna teekshna rooksha vidaahinah;

Aahaaraah raajasasyeshtaa duhkhashokaamayapradaah

(Bhagvat Gita chapter 17, verse 9)

All sorts of spicy food such as panipuri, chat, pickles, cooked fries, and curries are included in Rajasik aharas. Rajasik ahara gift us pain, grief, and disease. Usually, rajasik aharas are tasted bitter, sour, saline, very hot, dry, pungent, and burned. We prefer such kinds of foods during our feast which need to be controlled to protect us from the severity of the disease. Though we cannot avoid rajasik aharas in day-to-day life, still we should control the amount of such foods and try to increase the amount of satwik ahara in day-to-day food.

Excessive chilly results in stomach ulcers, gallbladder issues, acid reflux, and irritable bowel syndrome, excessive salt causes a rise in excessive thirst, bloating, and blood pressure. Its long-term effects are cardiac arrest, kidney stones, osteoporosis, stomach cancer, and ulcers. Excessive bitter food reduces the sexual ability of males. Excessive hot drinks like tea or coffee may cause esophageal cancer. Excessive colds like ice creams and cold drinks slow down the digestive process.

यातयामं गतरसं पूति पर्युषितं च यत् ।

उच्छिष्टमपि चामेध्यं भोजनं तामसप्रियम् ॥ १० ॥

Yaatayaamam gatarasam pooti paryushitam cha yat;

Ucchishtamapi chaamedhyam bhojanam taamasapriyam

(Bhagavat Gita Chapter 17, verse 10)

Tamasik ahara are rotten, impure, stale, tasteless. All kinds of drugs, alcohol, and non-vegetarian foods are all tamasik aharas. These tamasik aharas usually develop anger, intolerance, irritation, anxiety, aggressiveness, and sexual appetite which are destructive by nature. It spoils the calmness of the mind and the peace of the family. Sometimes it aggravates the minds to commit crimes and destroys all other humanitarian values. These foods are the storehouse of different diseases and bad tendencies for which they should be avoided except the use for some specific medicinal purposes only.

Positive effects of sprouts, salads:

SL. No	Food items	Nutrients	Advantages
1	Green gram	Vit-B, C, K	Improves cardiovascular health, digestion, eyesight, prevents anaemia, controls weight,
2	Chickpea	Folate, Manganese, Calcium, Magnesium, Potassium, Phosphorus, copper, Zinc, Vitamin-A, C, E	Lowers blood sugar level, prevents from blood pressure, reduces inflammation, maintains body weight, bone health, and muscle, may reduce irritable bowel syndrome, colon cancer
3	Carrot	Beta carotene, antioxidants, Vitamin A, C, K	Improves eyesight and skin, regulates blood pressure, and level of blood sugar, and reduces the risk of heart disease, cancer
4	Pomegranate	Iron, Magnesium, Potassium, Vitamin-C, E, Antioxidants	Prevents anaemia, improves skin health, lowers blood pressure, and

			cholesterol, reduces the risk of heart diseases, helps in healing wounds, prevents tooth decay, protects from Alzheimer's disease, and Parkinson's, and healthy prostate and breast tissue.
5	Groundnut	Vitamin C, E, Potassium, Magnesium, fiber, fatty acid, antioxidants, flavonoids, folate	Reduces blood sugar level, and inflammation, maintains blood pressure, cures eczema, provides healthy skin, reduces risk of cardiovascular diseases, improves memory, and fertility in men and women, antidepressants.
6	Coconut	Iron, manganese, magnesium, Copper, selenium, Vitamin-C, B antioxidants (gallic acid, salicylic acid), antibacterial, carbohydrate, fat, fiber	Maintains cholesterol, reduces inflammation, treats diarrhoea, prevents root canal infections, bone health improves, helps in RBC produces formation, keeps sugar control, protects against damage of cells
7	Guava	Fiber, Vitamin- C, K, Potassium, antioxidant, fiber	Improves blood sugar control, lowers blood pressure, and bad cholesterol and increases good cholesterol, prevents constipation, reduces the intensity of diarrhoea, enhances immunity
8	Horse gram	Calcium, iron, polyphenols, flavonoids, protein, phytosterol	Reduces high blood sugar, antioxidant, diuretic, removes

		esters	kidney stones and prevents their formation, heals peptic and mouth ulcers, relaxes in breathing problems, manages obesity, keeps warm in winter, regulates menstrual cycle
9	Finger millet	Amino acids, carbohydrates, fiber, iron, calcium, potassium, phytate, polyphenols, antioxidants, phytochemicals	Recovers from anaemia, controls blood sugar levels, strengthens bone, is helpful in anxiety, depression, insomnia, and migraine, reduces the risk of cardiovascular disease, and neurodegenerative diseases, and prevents constipation. People having kidney stones should avoid finger millet.
10	sesame	Phytosterols, Calcium, Selenium, Magnesium, Copper, Zinc, Iron, omega-6 fatty acid, Vitamin-B6, E, amino acid	Controls cholesterol, develops WBC, prevents osteoporosis, controls blood pressure, relaxes in stress, removes constipation, promotes hair growth

All these Indian foods are very much beneficial and supply adequate vitamins, and nutrition without having any side effects for the consumers. We should include at least one of them in our everyday menu.

Food and water relationship:

The human body contains around 5 liters of blood, Blood is considered as the flow of life and water is a liquid form of life. Blood is known as connective tissue as it connects

different body organs in physiology and different relations in society. Water is responsible for the purification of blood and the fitness of the heart and kidneys. Medical science recommends 3-4 Litres of safe drinking water per day for an adult. Drinking water should be lukewarm as to cope with the internal body parts. Water that is too hot or cold is not hygienic for the human body.

अजीर्णे भेषजं वारि, जीर्णे वारि बलप्रदम्।

भोजने चामृतं वारि, भोजनान्ते विषप्रदम्॥

(Chanakya niti)

In case of indigestion, the water is medicine, when taken after digestion, it increases the strength of the body, when sipped along with food, water works like nectar and just after food, it works like a poison.

Science of food and physiology:

Ayurveda has proved that our body is biologically organised on the basis of vata, pita and kapha. An adequate amount of particular food possesses the capacity of balancing all of them. We should know the positive effects of different foods, balancing and controlling these three fundamental tridoshas. Let us focus on some particular foods in relation to these vatta, kapha, and pitta here under.

Vatta -reducing and Kapha -generating foods	Dairy, coconut milk, avocado, butter, ghee, rice porridge, meat soup
Pitta pacifying foods	Cooling foods- fresh fruits, dates
Kapha reducing foods	Refreshing but warm foods- vegetable soup, bitter greens

Food and time relationship:

Sl No	Food time	Adequate food	Restricted food
1	Morning (6.00 AM TO 9.00 AM)	light warm, easy-to-digest foods, hot cereals, cooked fruits, barley, brown rice, wheat, fibre-rich foods, green leafy vegetables, green gram, pomegranate, amla, milk, butter, honey, pink salt	Spicy, salty, heavy meal, pickles, red meat, cold cereals, cold milk, cold juice, raw fruits, dehydrated fruits, black gram, maida, packaged foods, junk foods, prawns, radishes, Iced water, milk, caffeinated beverages, carbonated beverages, alcohol, milk
	Lunch	Rice, lentil or bean or paneer, two or three kinds of vegetables, lassi, warm salad or soup, healthy fat- ghee for vatta, pitta, and olive oil for Kapha	Iced water, milk, caffeinated beverages, carbonated beverages, alcohol, milk
	Mid-morning snack	Fresh fruits,vatta- mango, pitta- sweet orange, kapha- apple	Caffeine beverages, Iced water, milk, caffeinated beverages, carbonated beverages, alcohol, milk
	Mid-afternoon snack	Soaked almonds for Vatta, sunflower or pumpkin seeds for Pitta or Kapha	Iced water, milk, caffeinated beverages, carbonated beverages, alcohol, milk
	Night (7 PM-8	Protein, fat one dish	Sweet, Iced water, milk,

	PM)	vegetable grain mix dish or a vegetable or lentil soup with a whole wheat chapatti	caffeinated beverages, carbonated beverages, alcohol, milk
	Bedtime	Vatta-Warm milk with nutmeg, Pitta-warm milk with cardamom, Kapha- warm milk with ginger	Curd, fruits, no cold, alcohol

Fennel seeds, Amalaki, and Triphala can enhance digestion after a meal.

Avoid milk with sour and salty foods, fish with curd, or grilled meat, melons with deep-fried foods, cheese, and heavy grains. Honey should never be heated or cooked.

Significance of Anna Brahma:

Anna or rice is one of the normal carbohydrate foods in our country. Rice is considered as anna brahma because it possesses some microchemical potentialities to grasp the thoughts and feelings of the cook, unlike any other food. feelings of love, anger, and harmful attitudes are easily contaminated through food. So, rice cooked with the hand of one's mother or wife is healthier than that prepared and served in a hotel. So, it was a tradition in the Brahmin culture that rice from antisocial diseased croquet or uncleaned persons was not acceptable by the spiritual practice on us because the contamination of negative thoughts usually disturbs the mind during yoga and meditation.

Research in medical science has proved that rice possesses so many good qualities promoting positive health conditions both for children and adults. Rice is low in fat and sodium which prevents cardiovascular diseases and high blood pressure. It fights against cancerous cells having fiber and devoid of gluten. People who take rice in their lunch or dinner get protection from sleeplessness. The intervention of rice reduces the level of blood plasma eotaxin-1 level. So, it is proved that rice rice-based diet improves the quality of brain health and has certain effects on human minds.

Positive food habits for young children:

1. We should take food only on an empty stomach,
2. Hungry time is the best feeding time,
3. Taking food to the fullest capacity means making waste of food.
4. We should imagine the space of our stomach in four parts, two for food, one part for water, and one for air.
5. Eating in the sitting position is better than other positions.
6. Eating while standing may cause harm to internal body parts.
7. Home-made food is always better than the foods in the market.
8. We should always take our age and weight-specific balanced diet.
9. Taking food in anger and grief creates negative hormones in the body.
10. Urination before and after food is good for health.
11. Washing hands for sterilisation is hygienic for all.
12. Resting after lunch and walking after dinner support for easy digestion.
13. Taking fried food along with nonveg food is subject to food poisoning which should not be taken together.
14. Taking very hot and very cold food together is harmful to teeth, stomach, and skin.
15. Maida, salt, and sugar are taken as three white poisons whose use should be minimised
16. The manufacturing and expiring date on every packed food should be verified before their use.
17. Regional food and seasonal food are better for our health on the grounds of their availability and nature-friendly components.
18. Salt with milk is unhygienic which needs to be avoided.
19. Watching TV or smart phone while eating affects the digestive system and develops obesity and overeating habits.
20. Swallowing without chewing is subject to less secretion of digestive juices.

Conclusion:

God is the source of the entire creation. Jiva Satta is the part of the god. We should try to realise the goodness and goodness within our food. So, lord Shri Krishna has announced in chapter 15, verse 14 of Bhagavat Gita that:

अहं वैश्वानरो भूत्वा प्राणिनां देहमाश्रितः ।

प्राणापानसमायुक्तः पचाम्यन्नं चतुर्विधम् ॥ १४ ॥

Aham vaishwaanaro bhootwaa praaninaam dehamaashritah;

Praanaapaana samaayuktah pachaamyannam chaturvidham

It means God is the fire of digestion in every living body. He is the air of life, prana or apana (outgoing and incoming), by which he digests the four kinds of foodstuff such as charbya means which are chewed for example puffed rice, chosya which are sucked for example ripe mango, palm, lehya which are licked food, for example, pickle, ghee, and peya for example water, soup, milk.

If we carry out the commands or orders of our Guru, Grantha, and Govinda in selecting, adopting, preparing, and offering food with a feeling of surrender, all disorders of life must be abolished with a divine touch. Let us try to follow the Indian traditional food patterns and strengthen our body, mind, and spirit to continue our sadhana and fight against all sorts of illnesses that exist in the modern age.

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